

Identifying *kaige* and (proto-)Lucianic readings in 2 Kings with the help of Old Latin manuscript La¹¹⁵ 1

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The value of Old Latin (OL) witnesses in the textual criticism of Septuagint (LXX) has been lately noted by a growing number of scholars.² However, a systematic study of these witnesses and their textual affiliations has until recently been scarce and quite wanting.³ In this article the challenge is taken up to chart the possible (proto-)Lucianic, Old Greek (OG),⁴ and *kaige* readings in 2 Kings with the help of the 5th century OL manuscript *Palimpsestus Vindobonensis* (La¹¹⁵).⁵ Especially when the readings of La¹¹⁵ agree with the Antiochian text (*L*) against the majority text, the reading is of great interest, since these readings have the most potential for shedding light on the character of the Lucianic text (*L*) of 2 Kgs as well.

In earlier studies of La¹¹⁵ it has been generally concluded that its Greek base text was old and of good quality.⁶ There seems to be no Hexaplaric corruption in the manuscript. The same is likely the case for Vulgate as well. The question of *kaige* influence in the manuscript has so far not been much discussed, since no systematical studies on its text in the *kaige* sections have been conducted prior to this paper. However, those studies that have discussed the issue generally conclude that the *kaige* influence is either non-existent or, at most, very limited.⁷ This makes the manuscript an extremely interesting – and potentially valuable – witness to the study of the OG of 2 Kgs. Because of its old age, it is likely that La¹¹⁵ has – at least for the most part – avoided also Lucianic corruption.⁸

In addition to these considerations, some unique textual characteristics of La¹¹⁵ in 2 Kgs should be briefly noted. Unlike any other witness, La¹¹⁵ has some notable transpositions of materials in its chapters 10 and 17, and chapter 16 is missing from between verses 15:38 and 17:1.⁹ In chapter 10

¹ I would like to thank Tuukka Kauhanen for his kind remarks when writing this paper, and Pablo Torrijano and Julio Treballe, the editors of Göttingen Septuagint edition of 1–2 Kings, for an access to their preliminary apparatus.

² See especially Tuukka Kauhanen, *Lucifer of Cagliari*; Julio Treballe, “Readings of the Old Latin,” 120–45; Eugene Ulrich, *The Dead Sea Scrolls and the Origins of the Bible*, 233–89.

³ The three most systematic studies have been conducted by Antonio Moreno, *Las Glosas Marginales*; and Tuukka Kauhanen, *Proto-Lucianic Problem of 1 Samuel*; idem, *Lucifer of Cagliari*. For a systematic study of the text of La¹¹⁵ in 1 Kings, see Timo Tekoniemi, “Is there a (proto-)Lucianic stratum.”

⁴ The term “proto-Lucianic reading” is often used as a synonym for an Old Greek reading, especially in the context of 2 Kings. However, in this article this term simply denotes a reading that was extant in the base text of the Lucianic reviser(s), whether OG or not. Not all readings in this text form could have been original Old Greek readings – at least some corruption (accidental mistakes, pluses/minuses of varying length, etc.) must have taken place. Proto-Lucianic readings could therefore be divided in two groups: the original Old Greek readings and proto-Lucianic secondary readings.

⁵ See Bonifatius Fischer, “Palimpsestus Vindobonensis,” 13–87, for the edition of the manuscript.

⁶ See Kauhanen, “Septuagint in the West”; Tekoniemi, “Is there a (proto-)Lucianic stratum.”

⁷ To my knowledge only Julio Treballe, “Textos «Kaige» en la *Vetus Latina*,” 198–209, has argued that there might be some (albeit very limited) *kaige* influence in the manuscript. On the methodology of finding *kaige* readings, see Kauhanen, “Lucifer of Cagliari and the *Kaige* Revision,” 146–68.

⁸ The question whether (or to which extent) La¹¹⁵ has been influenced by the Lucianic revision is still up to debate, since both Kauhanen, *Proto-Lucianic Problem*, 163–4, and Tekoniemi, “Is there a (proto-)Lucianic stratum,” (forthcoming), maintain that there may be some (very) sporadic Lucianic influence in the manuscript. Thus an agreement between *L* and La¹¹⁵ does not by itself yet guarantee an Old Greek reading (see also footnote 4 above).

⁹ It is likely that chapter 16 was originally situated after chapter 17 in La¹¹⁵, since verse 15:38 mentions Ahaz as the son of Jotham as in the rest of the tradition. Why this chapter was transposed is not clear, but may have something to do with the peculiar chronological situation of chapters 2 Kgs 15–18.

La¹¹⁵ also has a curious “double narrative” of Jehu destroying the temple of Baal, which is partly resounded also by *L*. Why these phenomena appear is not yet completely clear, but it has been argued, quite persuasively in my opinion, that many of these “deviations” from rest of the Greek evidence may in fact be due to the OG nature of La¹¹⁵’s text.¹⁰

According to my calculations there are altogether 248 cases in which an agreement pattern can be observed. The distribution according to different patterns is as follows:¹¹

Pattern	Number of cases	Percentage of cases	Percentages in 1 Kgs ¹²
La ¹¹⁵ = B ≠ L	35	14%	27% (51 cases)
La ¹¹⁵ = L ≠ B	87	35%	26% (50 cases)
La ¹¹⁵ = B L ≠ A	4	1%	9% (16 cases)
La ¹¹⁵ = A ≠ B L	2	1%	2% (4 cases)
La ¹¹⁵ = other MSS ≠ A B L	28	11%	11% (21 cases)
Unique readings	92	38%	25% (48 cases)

When compared with the data from 1 Kings, the picture is quite clear: as would be expected from potential OG witnesses in the *kaige* sections, the amount of agreements between La¹¹⁵ and *L* increases while the agreements between B and La¹¹⁵ decrease. It is interesting, however, that the amount of unique readings also increases in La¹¹⁵. While in 1 Kings most of the unique readings could easily be attributed to small independent changes or translation technique (explications of subjects, additions of conjunctions, etc.), in 2 Kings the differences are much more substantial. Whether or not this is due to the influence of *kaige* in every other witness (even *L*) or even some putative revision on the part of La¹¹⁵ itself, this paper may help us define more clearly the general textual affiliations of La¹¹⁵ in 2 Kings.

Analyses of cases La¹¹⁵ = L ≠ B

Of all the 87 cases of pattern La¹¹⁵ = L ≠ B only a handful (15 cases in 10 verses) of the most significant and/or challenging cases can be analyzed here.¹³ These cases could help our understanding of the textual affiliations of La¹¹⁵ with *kaige*, (proto-)Lucianic text and other text forms.

6:8 εἰς τὸν τόπον τόνδε τινὰ ἐλμῶνι παρεμβάλω (תִּי תַּחֲבֹל מִן אֶלְמָנִי אֶלְמָנִי מִן אֶלְמָנִי MT)

La¹¹⁵: *in locum phelmunim insidia faciamus et fecerunt*

τόνδε τινὰ] > τόνδε 247 488; > δε τινὰ 158; > τινὰ 82 489 71 342; om L⁻⁸² 246 158; *illo et illo*
Vulg

¹⁰ See for the transposition of Elisha’s death narrative Richelle, *Testament*, 11–87; for the Jehu “double narrative” Schenker, *Älteste Textgeschichte*, 149–67; and for the textual situation of 2 Kgs 17 Trebolle, “Textual Pluralism,” 213–26, and Tekoniemi, “On the Verge.” In most of these cases even *L* would have arguably been subjected to the Hebraizing *kaige* revision.

¹¹ As the space does not permit the enumeration of all the cases in this article, the collected cases (of both 1 and 2 Kings) may be found and freely downloaded at www.helsinki.academia.edu/TimoTekoniemi.

¹² The numbers are taken from Tekoniemi, “Is there a (proto-)Lucianic stratum?”

¹³ The large and substantial agreements between La¹¹⁵ and *L* in 10:23–28 have to be skipped here, as they would need a whole paper of their own. It may be here said that many of the agreements between *L* and La¹¹⁵ in chapter 10 are for the most part certainly proto-Lucianic, and very probably go back to OG.

ελμῶνι] pr τὴν 71 342; φελμῶνι/-μουνει 247 488 98' 158; τόν (τοῦ 19') φελμουνει L⁻⁸² 246 460; *phelmunim* La^M

παρεμβάλῳ] ποιήσωμεν ἔνεδρον 127*; ποιήσωμεν ἔνεδρον καὶ ἐποίησαν L^{-82 127} 246 460;¹⁴ *insidia faciamus et fecerunt* La¹¹⁵; *obsessionem faciamus* La^M; *ponamus insidias* Vulg

In this verse there is a curious transcription ελμῶνι, which has not been discussed very much in the research. It seems probable that the OG translator did not know the meaning of the Hebrew expression יָנִי וְיָנִי, “such and such,” since also in 1 Sam 21:3 they are simply transcribed as Φελλανι Αλεμῶνι.¹⁵ In L⁻⁸² La¹¹⁵ La^M only the first word φελμουνει, which seems like some sort of mixed form of both words, is here transcribed with the second one missing, while the majority text has both a working translation of the construct (τόνδε τινὰ “this certain”) and a transcription ελμῶνι for the latter Hebrew word.

The amalgam φελμουνει may be an accidental one (either in the Hebrew *Vorlage* or not as likely in Greek), but is already known in Hebrew; cf. Dan 8:13 (יָנִי וְיָנִי).¹⁶ Therefore the difference could simply go back to differing copying practices in Hebrew, with one copyist writing the longer (MT) and other the shorter (L) form of the same expression. Hobbs proposes that L simply takes the reading from Dan,¹⁷ but this does not seem very likely, since this verse and Dan 8:13 have nothing else in common, and especially when the OL witnesses are taken into account – the reading seems proto-Lucianic, as Lucianic reviser would have almost certainly preferred the good Greek form τόνδε τινὰ of the majority text, had he known it. Peshitta (ܠܗܘܢܝܢ) lacks the mention of יָנִי וְיָנִי as well.

The question remains which reading was in the OG. The readings of Aquila and Symmachus would seem to indicate that the *better* Greek variant τόνδε τινὰ of majority text is here likely later.¹⁸ Whether this was already the reading of *kaige*, however, is not certain. In any case, the attestation of the Ethiopic *in regione Felmon* gives further proof for the antiquity of the reading of L and OL.

The awkward MT reading יָנִי וְיָנִי, often translated as “my encampment,” has been often thought to be corrupted, which it undeniably is.¹⁹ Majority text seems to take this as a first person verbal form of הָנִיחַ, “to encamp,” with the usual translation equivalent παρεμβάλλω, while L and OL witnesses – and even Vulgate – read differently “we make ambush.”²⁰ Of these maj. is closer to the Masoretic wording, and is probably due to *kaige*, both Hebraizing the reading and at the same time making the text a bit more readable. The reading of L OL Vulg. is partly in line with verse 6:9, where all Greek and OL witnesses have κέκρυπται²¹/ἔνεδρεύουσιν²² L (נָהַבִּים*) against MT’s strange form נָהַבִּים,

¹⁴ MS 158 has this plus erroneously in verse 12.

¹⁵ However, this transcription in 1 Sam could be a later addition in LXX, since it is lacking in the majority text.

¹⁶ Thus Burney, *Kings*, 285: “...this form appears to be presupposed by Luc....”

¹⁷ Hobbs, *2 Kings*, 71.

¹⁸ α’ προς τον τοπον τον δεινα τονδε τινα σ’ κατα τοπον τονδε.

¹⁹ Stade, *Kings*, 205.

²⁰ La¹¹⁵ translates the verb παρεμβάλλω four times: 1 Sam 4:1 *castra posuerunt*, 11:1 *castra posuit*; 2 Sam 11:11 *requiescent* (contextual harmonization?), 17:26 *castra constituit*. As there seems to be some contextual variation in the translations of this expression, also here the *insidia faciamus* could, to some extent, be argued to be such a “free” rendering.

²¹ La¹¹⁵ translates κρύπτω in 1 Sam 3:17 (*abscondere, absconderis*), 3:18 (*celavit*), 20:22 (*absconsus est*), 14:22 (*absconsi erant*); 2 Kgs 6:9 (*absconsa est*).

²² The verb ἔνεδρεύω is also used in 1 Sam 15:5 (אָרַב); 2 Sam 3:27 (בָּצִי), showing that already the translator was indeed familiar with it. The verb is used especially in Judges, where it consistently translates אָרַב.

which many commentators emend to the LXX's reading.²³ However, this reading of 6:8, while probably closer to the OG in *L* and *OL*, seems somewhat paraphrasing (or, alternatively, this was a somewhat free rendering already in the OG), and does not seem to come straight from Hebrew.²⁴ The use of the word ἔνεδρον in both verses 8 and 9 in *L* is suspicious and likely recensional, at least in 6:9. As both *OL* witnesses seem to follow a text very similar to *L* here, this seems like a recensional Lucianic reading, though the exact *Vorlage* of the *OL* witnesses is hard to discern – it is not certain that they follow exactly the wording of *L*, for instance.²⁵ The original Hebrew possibly had in verse 6:9 the form *תְּהַבֵּר.²⁶

On the other hand the plus of *L*⁸² *La*¹¹⁵ “and they made” at the end of the verse is quite clearly a secondary, explicative addition,²⁷ which was hardly made in both independently. In *kaige* sections the differentiation between recensional Lucianic and proto-Lucianic readings is difficult, but taking into account the other phenomena in the verse, this plus should probably be seen as proto-Lucianic, and ultimately as the OG reading (the secondary plus being extant already in the *Vorlage*), *kaige* having likely deleted the unnecessary explicative addition not found in *MT*.²⁸

6:13 καὶ εἶπεν δεῦτε ἴδετε ποῦ οὗτος

*La*¹¹⁵: *et dixit ite et videte ubi sit hic*

δεῦτε] πορεύεσθαι καὶ 460; πορεύθητε καὶ *L*⁸² 246; + καὶ 247 82 488; *ite et La*¹¹⁵

The translation δεῦτε (“come on!, come hither!”) for כּוּל is a clear *kaige* feature, as this translation only starts to appear in *kaige* sections.²⁹ This characteristic has been previously suggested by Héctor Avalos,³⁰ and is here further confirmed by *La*¹¹⁵, with it and *L* coinciding in the OG reading, “go!” The plus of καὶ could well be just a stylistic addition in both traditions independently, as likely shown by 247 488, and can hardly be used as evidence for any kind of (proto-)Lucianic influence.

10:8 καὶ εἶπεν θέτε αὐτὰς βουνοὺς δύο παρὰ τὴν θύραν τῆς πόλης εἰς πρωί

*La*¹¹⁵: *et dixit ieu ponite ea et illa e duobus ordinibus in porta civitatis usque mane*

θύραν τῆς πόλης Rahlfs]³¹ θύραν τῆς πόλης πόλεως *B*^{xt*}; πόλην τῆς πόλεως *L*-700 460; θύραν τῆς πόλεως *rel*; *in porta civitatis La*¹¹⁵; *introitum portae Vulg*; וַיִּצְוֶה מַתְּנָה *MT*

²³ See Stade, *Kings*, 205. Peshitta seems to also have in 6:8 a similar double reading: “in such and such place you shall set an ambush and hide” (אֲבִיחֶם וְאֲסַחֵם בְּכַל יְהִיבֵם).

²⁴ Similarly Stade, *Kings*, 205.

²⁵ The *Vorlage* of *La*¹¹⁵ in the case of *insidia* may have been ἔνεδρον, but as this is quite a rare word in LXX, this becomes suspect. In 2 Kgs 17:4 *insidia* seems to translate ἐπιβουλὴν (against the ἀδικίαν of majority text), found again only in Lucianic witnesses. The *Vorlage* of *La*¹¹⁵ is therefore not completely certain.

²⁶ Thenius, *Könige*, 300.

²⁷ Thusly already Rahlfs, *Lukian*, 274–5. On the other hand Burney, *Kings*, 285, prefers this reading as “a suitable introduction to v. 9.”

²⁸ It is also possible that this plus was dropped at a very early point because of a homoioteleuton καὶ...καὶ, and the proto-Lucianic tradition was the only one to preserve the plus. There would be therefore no need to suppose *kaige* influence here. See somewhat similarly also Kreuzer, *Bible in Greek*, 287–8.

²⁹ In 2 Kgs 1:2, 6, 6:2, 13, 19, 7:4, 14, 22:13.

³⁰ Héctor Avalos, “ΔΕΥΡΟ/ΔΕΥΤΕ,” 168–73. In fact, already Rahlfs, *Lucian*, 179–80, made notion of this characteristic, but could not of course ascribe the phenomenon to *kaige* revision – instead, as is well known, he argued for the exact opposite, namely, that the Lucianic text had been revised, rather than the *B*-text.

³¹ No manuscript gives the reading found in Rahlfs' edition, as also indicated by his apparatus.

Cf. 10:9 ἔστη A B 56 245 Arm Syr] κατέστη ἐν τῇ πύλῃ τῆς πόλεως L-700 460; + ἐν τῷ πυλῶνι τῆς πόλεως rel; *stetit in porta civitatis* La¹¹⁵; תַּחֲנִיחַ MT

There are two interesting textual phenomena here. First, the equivalent of θύρα for the Hebrew “תַּחֲנִיחַ” seems to be a *kaige* feature, as can be seen by both the distribution between *kaige*/non-*kaige* sections and by the manuscript attestation.³² The OG equivalent of תַּחֲנִיחַ seems to have been πυλῶν/θυρώμα. Interestingly the OG equivalent θύρα ~ “תַּחֲנִיחַ” keeps the same throughout all of the books and does not change like with many other *kaige* readings.³³

Second, the whole phrase תַּחֲנִיחַ תַּחֲנִיחַ, “the doorway of the gate” (=θύρα τῆς πύλης) seems to be in Samuel-Kings more characteristic to MT/*kaige* edition than to OG.³⁴ In OG, as here in 2 Kgs 10:8–9, the usual word combination is “the gate of the city” (most probably from תַּחֲנִיחַ תַּחֲנִיחַ). That this was the original Greek reading also in *kaige* sections can be ascertained partly by La¹¹⁵, as here both *L* and La¹¹⁵ give the original reading. It seems that for some reason in MT or in the *Vorlage* of OG the phrase was quite systematically changed. MT has in 1 Kgs 17:10 the phrase תַּחֲנִיחַ תַּחֲנִיחַ, “the gate of the city,” which may hint at the change to have happened in MT.³⁵

10:10 ἴδετε ἀφῶ ὅτι οὐ πεσεῖται ἀπὸ τοῦ ῥήματος κυρίου εἰς τὴν γῆν

La¹¹⁵: *scitote et videte quia non cadent verba domini in terram*

ἴδετε ἀφῶ] > ἀφῶ L-700 246 460; *scitote et videte* La¹¹⁵; *ut sciant cuncti* La^M;

אִתָּהּ וְעַתָּה MT

The simple transcription of the somewhat rare Hebrew conjunction אִתָּהּ, “then,” is missing from *L* and La¹¹⁵, possibly telling of *kaige* influence in the majority text. Similar transcription ἀφῶ is found only once elsewhere in 2 Kgs 2:14, where it is shared by all manuscripts, save for the Lucianic 82. It is hard to say whether the transcription goes back to the OG translator in 2:14, since the textual situation of this verse is somewhat problematic already in itself.³⁶ If Treballe is right in asserting that the transcription ἀφῶ is due to *kaige* in 2:14, and the *L* plus καὶ οὗτος the OG, the coinciding minus of *L* La¹¹⁵ here in 10:10 would likely go back to OG, as well.³⁷ On the other hand it would also suit

³² This feature has also been discussed by Muraoka, “Greek Texts of Samuel-Kings,” 44, who nevertheless does not outright deem this as a *kaige* feature. Cf. תַּחֲנִיחַ in 1 Sam 2:22 (>OG; θύρας in Hexaplaric witnesses); 2 Sam 10:8 (θύρα/θύραν A B M O a⁻⁵²⁷ b 64’ 55 158 244 245 460 707] πυλῶνα rel), 11:9 (θύρα] πυλῶνι *L* = *portam* La¹¹⁵), 11:23 (θύρας in all witnesses); 1 Kgs 6:8[13] (πυλῶν), 6:31[30] (θυρώματι), 6:33[31] (πυλῶνι), 7:5[42] (θυρώματα), 14:6 (ανοιγματι A 247 127 CII⁻³²⁸ 121 d⁻³⁷⁰ s⁻⁶⁴ 554 =Hex.), 14:27 (πυλῶνα), 17:10 (πυλῶνα), 19:13 (>OG; the translator mistakenly(?) read תַּחֲנִיחַ as תַּחֲנִיחַ), 22:10 (πύλαις); 2 Kgs 4:15 (θύραν in all witnesses), 5:9 (θύρα(ι)ς in all witnesses), 7:3 (θύραν] πύλην 246 71 55; πύλη 460), 23:8 (θύρα(v) in all witnesses).

³³ In 1 Sam 3:15, 21:14, 23:7; 2 Sam 13:17, 18; 1 Kgs 6:31, 32, 34 (3x), 7:50 (2x), 16:34; 2 Kgs 4:4, 5, 33, 6:32 (2x), 9:3, 10, 18:16. Only in 2 Kgs 12:10 is the translation different, but this variant seems to be due to translation technique.

³⁴ In 2 Sam 10:8 (πύλης A B^{ixl.c pr m} M O a⁻⁵²⁷ 121 64’ 55 244 245 460 707] πολεως rel), 11:23 (πύλης] πυλωνος L^{-93 127}; πολεως 93-127 CII^{-46’ 313} 488 71 245 372); 1 Kgs 22:10 (OG: ἐν ταῖς πύλαις Σαμαρείας); 2 Kgs 7:3 (θύραν τῆς πόλεως), 23:8 (θύραν τῆς πύλης). In 1 Sam 21:14 LXX has an interesting double reading ἐπὶ ταῖς θύραις τῆς πόλεως ... ἐπὶ τὰς θύρας τῆς πύλης. Because of the prevalence of the phenomenon, it seems unlikely that the changes are simply due to accidental graphical/phonetic confusion (ΠΥΛΗ ~ ΠΟΛΙΣ). A graphical confusion in Hebrew (תַּחֲנִיחַ ~ תַּחֲנִיחַ) would be much more probable, but, again, unlikely due to the somewhat systematic nature of the change.

³⁵ 1 Kgs 17:10: תַּחֲנִיחַ תַּחֲנִיחַ (πυλῶνα τῆς πόλεως).

³⁶ *Kaige* likely would have just left this word untranslated (unlike α’ καιπερ αὐτος and σ’ και νυν). The *Vorlage* of the majority text of 2 Kgs 2:14, however, likely had not the peculiar אִתָּהּ-וְעַתָּה of MT, but, as in 10:10, אִתָּהּ. It is possible, however, that 82, which lacks ἀφῶ in 2:14, is the only Lucianic manuscript to preserve the original minus, all other manuscripts having been subjected to *kaige*, but this does not seem very likely.

³⁷ Treballe, “Readings of the Old Latin,” 130–1. However, the reading in 2:14 is marked in 93-127 with asterisk, likely indicating late origins (derived from α’ αὐτος?).

the style of the OG translator to simply transcribe such a rare word if he was unsure of its translation. In such a case the minus of *L* La¹¹⁵ could be due to recensional stylizing (omission of an unnecessary and incomprehensible word). An accidental omission in either tradition does not seem likely. The case has to be left undecided, although the coinciding minus of *L* La¹¹⁵ would seem to warrant the label proto-Lucianic.

However, it needs to be noted that La¹¹⁵ has here also a double reading “know and perceive,” which is missing from other witnesses.³⁸ This is a somewhat frequent pair also in Hebrew.³⁹ The first verb *scitote* is also to be found in La^M *ut sciant*. The Latin witnesses may be thus somehow related, although the semantic fields of the two verbs might be close enough to be even considered as two differing translations of the same underlying Greek verb.⁴⁰ According to Fischer *scitote* corresponds to γνῶτε, which is found also in Aquila,⁴¹ and ultimately to the עָרַךְ of MT. Either the reading of La¹¹⁵ is thus a double translation of ἴδετε, a conflated reading of OG and Aquila, a (*kaige* type?) harmonization to the Hebrew idiom (independently or already in its the Greek *Vorlage*), or, very unlikely, it still preserves here the original Hebrew idiom עָרַךְ עָרַךְ, which later became corrupted (because of graphical confusion?) to the simple עָרַךְ of MT and רָא (ἴδετε) of LXX.⁴²

Although the decision is not an easy one, the simplest solution would be to see this as a double translation in La¹¹⁵, which possibly supplanted the Greek transcription αφφω.

10:11 καὶ ἐπάταξεν Ἰου ... πάντας τοὺς ἀδρούς αὐτοῦ καὶ τοὺς γνωστοὺς αὐτοῦ καὶ τοὺς ἱερεῖς αὐτοῦ
La¹¹⁵: *et percussit ... proximos eius et notos eius et sacerdotes idolorum eius*

πάντας 2°] om 125 La¹¹⁵

ἀδρούς] ἀγχιστεύοντας *L*-700 460; ἄνδρας 527; *proximos* La¹¹⁵; *cognatos eius et propinquos* La^M;
optimates Vulg; עָרַךְ עָרַךְ MT

αὐτοῦ 3°] + καὶ τοὺς ἀδρούς αὐτοῦ *L* 460

The equivalent ἀδρός for לוֹדָד (שׂא), “a mighty one,” has previously been suspected to be a *kaige* reading, but the conventional evidence has not been sufficient to definitely label it as such.⁴³ Instead

³⁸ It is unlikely this double reading has anything to do with the case above (αφφω). Even though either *scitote* or *videte* could be simply a guess made by the Latin translator, it is much more likely he would have simply transcribed the Greek further instead of making a (quite bad) guess.

³⁹ Cf. עָרַךְ עָרַךְ (=γνῶτε καὶ ἴδετε) in 1 Sam 12:17, 14:38; 1 Kgs 20:7; 2 Kgs 5:7. In 1 Sam 23:23 and Jer 5:1 the verbs are in reversed order.

⁴⁰ Kauhanen, “Septuagint in the West,” 309–10, has indeed proposed that La¹¹⁵ and La^M likely go back not to one single Old Latin translation, but at least two separate translations. 2 Kgs 10:10 could then be another case supporting his theory, unless *scitote* is here seen as the original translation, which was only later supplemented with the second translation *videte*, which is also closer to the Greek text.

⁴¹ Fischer, “Palimpsestus Vindobonensis,” 83. Cf. α’ γνῶτε καιπερ οτι ου πεσειται.

⁴² Interestingly also Symmachus seems to render with LXX only רָא instead of עָרַךְ: σ’ ἴδετε ουν νυν οτι ου πεσειται. Tuukka Kauhanen (personal correspondence) suggested me that it would not be impossible either that the double translation has been borne of an erroneous itacistic conflation of ἴδετε and οἶδατε. While an ingenious proposition, no evidence of such mistake is found in the Greek manuscripts.

⁴³ See Greenspoon, *Textual Studies*, 337–8. In 2 Kgs the term is also found in 10:6: καὶ οἱ υἱοὶ τοῦ βασιλέως ἦσαν ἐβδομήκοντα ἄνδρες οὗτοι ἄδρῳι (ἄνδρες οὗς οἱ ἄδρῳι *L*-700 *f* 158 245) τῆς πόλεως ἐξέτρεπον αὐτούς, which La¹¹⁵ translates as *et filii regis erant LXX et omnes maiores civitates nutriebant eos*. Thus instead of “men who were mighty,” La¹¹⁵ reads “all the mighty (ones).” The textual situation of La¹¹⁵ is not completely certain, however, since Fischer, “Palimpsestus Vindobonensis,” 83, proposes an emendation of *omnes maiores* to *homines (et) maiores*, which would bring the text to an agreement with the majority text. La¹¹⁵ usually uses *magnus* to translate the Greek μέγας or its cognates. The translation of La¹¹⁵ could, however, work even now with ἄδρῳι (a *kaige* reading?) as its *Vorlage*. Should

of τοὺς ἀδρούς αὐτοῦ, La¹¹⁵ has here the same text as *L* ἀγγιστεύοντας, “the nearest (ones),” backed up by La^M’s double reading/translation *cognatos eius et propinquos eius*, “his kinsmen and relatives.” Interestingly enough, *L* also gives the majority text’s reading καὶ τοὺς ἀδρούς αὐτοῦ as a plus at the end of its own list, indicating that this might be a *kaige* reading that was taken over by *L* and added to the end of its list.⁴⁴ La¹¹⁵ does not have this reading in either place, likely going back to a Greek text which had no mention of ἀδρούς.

The reading ἀγγιστεύοντας of *L* La¹¹⁵ seems to be a translation of Hebrew יִזְעָג, ⁴⁵ “kinsmen,” which is graphically very similar to the MT’s יִזְדָּג. There may have thus happened a graphical confusion in the copying process of either tradition. The reading of *L* La¹¹⁵ La^M would suit the context better, since the context is about the destruction of the whole seed of Ahab (given in OG in a logical order “his kinsmen, his friends, his priests”), part of which the “mighty ones” likely were not. Alternatively, the MT reading יִזְדָּג could also be explained as a deliberate harmonization towards 10:6, where the “mighty ones” are now found.⁴⁶ This harmonization may also be literary critically interesting, since in MT “the mighty ones” now seem to kill the sons of Ahab (10:6) and, unlike in OG, Jehu then in turn kills not only the relatives of Ahab, but also the “mighty ones” who were raising the sons (10:10). His picture is therefore enhanced towards a somewhat more ruthless image.⁴⁷

It seems in any case quite clear that at least here the word ἀδρός is indeed due to *kaige*, and, on the other hand, that the reading “the nearest ones” is proto-Lucianic, and most probably OG.⁴⁸ It may thus be concluded that ἀδρός as an equivalent for the Hebrew לֹאֵלֵךְ is indeed a certain *kaige* reading at least in one of the two cases in Kings.⁴⁹

10:29 πλὴν ἀμαρτιῶν Ιεροβοαμ ... οὐκ ἀπέστη Ιου ἀπὸ ὀπισθεν αὐτῶν αἱ δαμάλεις αἱ χρυσαῖ ἐν Βαιθηλ καὶ ἐν Δαν⁵⁰

La¹¹⁵: *set a peccatis hieroboam ... non discessit ieu rex set abit post vaccas peccati quae erant in bethel et in dan*

we then emend a working Latin text, possibly farther from MT than any other manuscript, to a suggested *kaige* reading? In any case, the now confused textual situation of 10:6 is due to some textual corruption, since even the MT construct כְּבָרֵי־אֲדָמָיִךְ אֲנָשֵׁי־בְנֵי־אֲדָמָיִךְ (“the heads of the men of the sons of your master”) is unnaturally long, and does not work in the logic of the narrative, since in 10:7–8 the sons themselves are killed.

⁴⁴ See for a somewhat similar case 1 Kgs 16:28d in Tekoniemi, “Is there a (proto-)Lucianic stratum,” 10.

⁴⁵ Cf. 2 Sam 14:11 (ἀγγιστέα) οἱ ἀγγιστεύοντες *L* 318 554^{me}. In 1 Kgs 16:11 manuscript A alone reads ἀγγιστεῖς, but this is quite clearly a Hexaplaric reading – OG lacks the end of the verse. Overall in Septuagint ἀγγιστεύω is one of the most common equivalents for the Hebrew verb לאג.

⁴⁶ It is likely that the whole mention of 10:6b, or at least the passage אֶת־זְדָּגֵי־הָעִיר מְגִדָּלִים אִתָּם, is originally an explicating gloss, bringing the “Ahab’s mighty” and Ahab’s seventy sons (cf. 10:7) only secondarily to the text. The mention of 6b is grammatically very awkwardly connected to the preceding text. If this is indeed the case, *L* La¹¹⁵ would likely have the most original reading in 10:11, which was later harmonized in MT towards this later gloss of 6b.

⁴⁷ Politically speaking, this course of action would only make sense to Jehu: the “mighty ones”, who were previously supposed to stay loyal to their king, now turn against their master by killing all his sons. How loyal would Jehu, a recent usurper, then expect them to be towards him?

⁴⁸ Thusly also Stade, *Kings*, 228.

⁴⁹ Besides 2 Kgs 10:6 and here, ἀδρός is also found a third time in 1 Kgs 1:9, but this case may be simply corruption from ἄνδρας (as given by A *L* 106 107 71 244 245 318 460 707 Arm Syr; om 509), unless the reading is Hexaplaric harmonization towards the MT אֲנָשֵׁי־יְהוָה. Even if this is not the case, this equivalent being found in a *kaige* section is still suspicious nonetheless. The word is once more encountered in 2 Sam 15:18 in a lengthy LXX (*kaige*?) plus not found in MT.

⁵⁰ This verse is full of small textual problems between MT/*L*/rel/La¹¹⁵. Because of the lack of space, only the most illuminating agreement between *L* and La¹¹⁵ will be here analyzed.

αἱ δαμάλεις αἱ χρυσαῖ] τῶν δαμάλεων τῆς ἀμαρτίας τῶν χρυσῶν *L*-700; *uaccas peccati* La¹¹⁵;
vaccarum peccati... La^M; בָּהֵיֶה יִלְגָּשׁ MT

In this verse we are told that Jehu, despite being a pious king, nevertheless did not stray from the cultic crime and main sin of Jeroboam, that is, his golden calves. Amongst the many textual problems of this verse, the most interesting case in this verse is the plus “of sin,” τῆς ἀμαρτίας, of *L*, which is also rendered by both OL witnesses La¹¹⁵ and La^M. The OL witnesses also completely lack the adjective “golden.” La^M is in its partiality hard to assess, but La¹¹⁵ does give enough hints to evaluate *L*’s reading. The lacking of the further description τῶν χρυσῶν indicates that La¹¹⁵ did not know the fuller text form of *L* and even more so B – if it did, it would have certainly given the second description as well. Accidental omission does not appear very likely. This reading seems thus like a proto-Lucianic reading. It does also have considerable probabilities for OG reading, as the “calves of sin” are nowhere else described as such – unlike the well-known “golden calves” of 1 Kgs 12:28, 32.⁵¹ A change from the usual “golden” to otherwise unknown calves “of sin” in proto-Lucianic stage does not seem very likely. La¹¹⁵ thus likely alone preserves the sole OG reading δαμάλεων τῆς ἀμαρτίας (*תאטת ילגש), to which *L* conflates the *kaige* correction τῶν χρυσῶν (=בהיה MT).

13:17 ...καὶ εἶπεν Ελισαιε τόξευσον καὶ ἐτόξευσεν καὶ εἶπεν Ελισαιε

La¹¹⁵: *et dixit helisseus sagittare et sagittavit et dixit helisseus*

Ελισαιε 1°... Ελισαιε 2°] om B

τόξευσον... Ελισαιε 2°] om *CII* d⁻³⁷⁰ 246 s⁻⁶⁴ 488

Ελισαιε 2°] om A *L*-700 460 La^M (=MT)

τόξευσον καὶ ἐτόξευσεν] ροιζησον 245; ροιζησον και εροιζησεν A Arm Syr (* a’); *sagittare et sagittavit* La¹¹⁵ La^M

It is quite clear that the lone minus of B is due to some accident in the transmission. This omission is easily explained if it is assumed that B had as its base text a text similar to that of (*kaige*/Hexaplaric?) A *L*-700 460, where the second mention of Ελισαιε is now missing, as in MT.⁵² In such a case a simple homoioteleuton mistake εἶπεν...εἶπεν could have taken place in B. Alexandrinus then supplies the text of Aquila, possibly because it had as its *Vorlage* the short B-text that needed emendation.⁵³ The majority text (or *L*) is hardly in any way dependent on this Hexaplaric reading ροιζησον και εροιζησεν.⁵⁴

The majority text could in fact be argued to stem from *kaige*, as the verb τοξεύω, albeit rarely, only starts to appear in the *kaige* sections of Samuel-Kings.⁵⁵ The equivalent used for the Hebrew רר in 1 Samuel 20:20, 36, 37, 31:3 is ἀκοντίζω, “to throw a javelin,” while τόξον is used in Samuel-

⁵¹ Also in 2 Chr 13:8 (and Ex 32).

⁵² The rest of the tradition has this second Ελισαιε, which is not found in the MT (ויאמר אלשישע ירה ויור ויאמר). It seems likely it has been omitted secondarily by A *L*-700 460 (La^M) due to Hexaplaric influence, and originally by *kaige* in B.

⁵³ The verb ροιζέω is used by Aquila to translate the Hebrew רר. The word τόξον, on the other hand, is used by Aquila to translate תִּשָּׁר; see Reider & Turner, *An Index to Aquila*, 211.

⁵⁴ *Contra* Torijano, “How Much Hexaplaric Material,” 114, who appears to consider this as a Hexaplaric reading.

⁵⁵ The equivalent is also mentioned by McLay, “*Kaige* and Septuagint Research,” 133, as a (disputed) *kaige*-variant (#55). Elsewhere in 2 Sam 11:20 (τοξεύσουσιν] τοξεουσιν A O^{-376c} 98-379 *CII*-328 a 509 44 s⁻⁶⁴ 71 342 460 707; πληγησεσθε L⁻⁸² 318; πληγησεσθαι B^{ms} 82 158), 11:24 *bis* (ἐτόξευσαν] κατεβαρυνθη *L* | οἱ τοξευοντες] τα βελη *L*); 2 Kgs 19:32. These attestations of *L* could similarly point to an interest on the part of *kaige* to use τοξεύω.

Kings to translate נִשְׁלַח, “bow.”⁵⁶ While the *kaige* origins of τοξεύω could be argued for, it is nevertheless more likely that this translation of the quite rare Hebrew verb נִשְׁלַח comes already from the OG translator, who was simply influenced in this passage by נִשְׁלַח to use an equivalent semantically closer to τόξον, since at least “throwing a javelin” clearly was not a possible translation of the Hebrew here. La¹¹⁵ *sagitto*, “shoot arrows,” likely attests the majority – and OG – reading here, while *L* gives a slightly Hebraized form of the text.

13:20 καὶ μονόζωνοι Μωαβ ἦλθον ἐν τῇ γῆ ἑλθόντος τοῦ ἐνιαυτοῦ.

La¹¹⁵: *et piratae moab venerunt in terram illam.*

μονόζωνοι] *piratae* La¹¹⁵; *praedones* La^M

Cf. 13:21 μονόζωνον] *πειρατήριον* *L* 460; *pirate* La¹¹⁵

ἑλθόντος τοῦ ἐνιαυτοῦ] > τοῦ 46' 246; om La¹¹⁵; *post annum* La^M; הַשָּׁנָה אָז MT

There are two phenomena to be assessed here. First it should be noted that μονόζωνος as a translation of נִשְׁלַח is a quite well-known *kaige* feature.⁵⁷ Multiple differing renderings for נִשְׁלַח are used in Samuel-Kings, but in the *kaige*-section μονόζωνος (“lightly armed (soldier)”) becomes the only one.⁵⁸ Here La¹¹⁵ confirms that this is indeed a *kaige* reading. Richelle notes accordingly that the OG most probably read *πειρατήρια*, a term used also by *L* in the next verse.⁵⁹ La^M seems to similarly translate a Greek text with *πειρατήρια*, reading *praedones*, “plunderer, robber.” It is interesting to note that *L* gives in this same verse first alone an OG historical present θάπτουσιν against the *kaige* aorist ἔθαψαν, and right after this a *kaige* reading μονόζωνος – and in the next verse it has furthermore clearly gone through recensional Lucianic stylizing. This showcases well the mixed text type of *L*, and how these three characteristics often go hand in hand in *L*.

In the second case already the formulation of MT הַשָּׁנָה אָז (possibly “year having gone”) has challenged scholars for over a century, and even some Hebrew manuscripts give a slightly differing text (הַשָּׁנָה בָּ; cf. Vulg. *in ipso anno*).⁶⁰ It is then interesting to note that in La¹¹⁵ this problematic chronological note is lacking completely. The lack does not seem to be due to any kind of apparent copying mistake, and the respective Greek reading should have been quite easy for the Latin translator to handle. Most probably thus already the *Vorlage* of La¹¹⁵ lacked this reading. Taking into account that in the following narrative 13:20–21 La¹¹⁵ seems to give a very old text (most probably OG, which should in turn be seen as the oldest version preserved),⁶¹ the possibility should be given thought that the lacking grammatically hard construct is in fact the oldest reading attainable.

On this line of thought, Schenker suggests that the chronological note may have been later added to make the happening more miraculous: even after a year the remains of Elisha were able of

⁵⁶ In 1 Sam 2:4, 31:3; 2 Sam 1:22, 22:35; 1 Kgs 22:35; 2 Kgs 6:22, 9:24, 13:15 *bis*, 16.

⁵⁷ McLay, “*Kaige* and Septuagint Research,” 131 (#11).

⁵⁸ The translator misread נִשְׁלַח instead of נִשְׁלַח, and therefore was forced to simply transcribe γεδουρ in 1 Sam 30:8, 15 (2x), 23. The word is translated in 2 Sam 3:22 (ἔξοδος); and in 2 Sam 4:2 and 1 Kgs 11:24 (σύστρεμμα). The *kaige* reading μονόζωνος can be elsewhere found in 2 Sam 22:30; 2 Kgs 5:2 (μονόζωνοι] + *πειρατήριον* V CI CII a d^{-68' 370} s^{-64' 55 244} 318 554), 6:23 (*πειραταί(ς)* *L* Syr), 13:21 (*πειρατήριον* *L*-700), 24:2 (4x, no variants, though some manuscripts lack some instances of the word).

⁵⁹ Richelle, *Testament*, 76. See for the evidence the note above.

⁶⁰ Cf. Stade, *Kings*, 245; Kittel, *Könige*, 259; and Klostermann, *2 Könige*, 439. De Rossi, *Variae Lectiones*, 243, lists two Masoretic Medieval manuscripts in favor of הַשָּׁנָה בָּ.

⁶¹ Similarly Richelle, *Testament*, 73–87. See for a full analysis of the narrative of 2 Kgs 13:20–21 Treballe, “*Dos Textos*,” 8–16.

miracles.⁶² However, it could also be that this mention was added so that the reader would not be confused about the mention of “bones” of the next verse: while in the Old Latin version the body could have still been fully intact without the bones yet showing, after a year this definitely would not have been the case. As this story follows directly the death and burial of Elisha, the reader does indeed get the impression that the actions could be temporally quite close to each other. Richelle also marks that when taking into account the generality of the overall story, the quite precise indication of time of MT/LXX is somewhat unexpected.⁶³

While debatable, I would make a cautious suggestion that La¹¹⁵ alone preserves here the OG – and thus the oldest text attainable. This seems to also be the case overall in the burial narrative 2 Kgs 13:20–21.

17:6 καὶ κατώκισεν αὐτοὺς ἐν Αλαε καὶ ἐν Αβωρ ποταμοῖς Γωζαν καὶ Ορη Μήδων

La¹¹⁵: *et conlocavit eos in civitatem mediorum in emath et ad flumen abyro usque in hunc diem*

ἐν Αλαε καὶ ἐν Αβωρ ποταμοῖς Γωζαν] *in civitatem*⁶⁴ *mediorum in emath et ad flumen abyro* La¹¹⁵;
in Ala et in Habor iuxta fluvium Gozan Vulg; גוֹזָן וְהַחֲבוֹר וְהַמְּדַי MT

Ορη Μήδων] ὄρει Μήδων 328 527; ἐν ὁρίοις Μήδων ἕως τῆς ἡμέρας ταύτης L-700 460; + ἕως τῆς ἡμέρας ταύτης CI 328 158 244 342; + *usque in hunc diem* La¹¹⁵; *in civitatibus Medorum* Vulg; מְדַי וְעָרֵי MT

The strange LXX rendering of the simple מְדַי וְעָרֵי, “the cities of Medes,” apparently as a transcription Ορη⁶⁵ Μήδων, is odd, but has incited surprisingly little comments in the research. The most interesting fact is that in La¹¹⁵ this reading is missing, and the proper translation “the city of Medians” is actually found in it, although in a differing position from MT/LXX.⁶⁶ It is known that sometimes the *kaige* revisers incorrectly transcribed common nouns as proper nouns.⁶⁷ This phenomenon seems to have taken place here as well, as the Ορη Μήδων now finishes the long list of different place names of Israelites’ exile. Since La¹¹⁵ hardly has any connection to *L* in this reading either,⁶⁸ it has probably here as the lone witness preserved the OG translation (*ἐν ταῖς πόλεσιν Μήδων).

Another OG reading to be found in La¹¹⁵, and this time also in *L*, is the verse-ending plus “until this day.” This term is recurrent in the chapter, and probably works here as an original

⁶² Schenker, *Älteste Textgeschichte*, 145.

⁶³ Richelle, *Testament*, 75.

⁶⁴ The editor, Fischer, “Palimpsestus Vindobonensis,” 87, suggests that the singular *civitatem mediorum* of La¹¹⁵ is simply an “error for *in civitates medorum*.” This could well be the case.

⁶⁵ While it is possible that this is simply a translation/misreading of הַר, “hill, mountain,” instead of MT’s עָרֵי, this does not seem likely, since in any case one would expect here a dative case (corrected to dat.sg. ὄρει in 328 527). *L* is easily explainable as contextual facilitation. Taking Ορη as a transcription (similar to NETS: “Ore of Medes”) seems therefore like the best option. Similarly Torijano, “Textual Criticism,” 210: “...the reading Ορη seems to lie at the origin of the rest of the Greek variants.” The translator would have apparently made the same mistake twice, as also in 2 Kgs 18:11 the same peculiar rendering is found. Furthermore, had he found Ορη in his base text, the translator of La¹¹⁵ would have easily been able to translate it correctly as *mons*, as he does in 1 Sam 14:22, 23; 2 Sam 13:34; 1 Kgs 11:43, 12:24o, 16:24.

⁶⁶ Torijano, “Textual Criticism,” 210, takes this reading as a possible sporadic corruption of Vulgate *in civitatibus Medorum*. While this is possible (though not exceedingly likely), it does not properly explain the lack of Ορη Μήδων in La¹¹⁵.

⁶⁷ Tov, “Transliterations of Hebrew Words,” 82, 88–9

⁶⁸ If La¹¹⁵ had the *L* reading ὁρίοις, “boundaries,” as its *Vorlage*, the translator would have likely been able to translate it correctly, as seen in 1 Sam 6:9 (*orbitae*), 12 (*fines*), 10:2 (*finibus*), 11:3, 7 (*regionem*).

literary/compositional marker.⁶⁹ There are also other proto-Lucianic and *kaige* readings to be found with the help of La¹¹⁵ in verses 17:3–6, already analyzed in-depth by Torijano.⁷⁰

17:17 καὶ ἐμαντεύοντο μαντείας καὶ οἰωνίζοντο καὶ ἐπράθησαν

La¹¹⁵: *et divinabant divinationes et fecerunt ephud et theraphin et augurabantur et auspicabantur καὶ οἰωνίζοντο*] + οἰωνισμοῖς καὶ ἐποίησαν ἐφοῦδ καὶ θεραφεῖμ L-700; + *et fecerunt ephud et theraphin* La¹¹⁵

This plus found in *L* has often been deemed a late (Lucianic) addition,⁷¹ and the addition of οἰωνισμοῖς is certainly Lucianic harmonization, added for better style. However, the witness of La¹¹⁵ helps us see that καὶ ἐποίησαν ἐφοῦδ καὶ θεραφεῖμ, “and they made *ephod* and *teraphim*,” might in fact be an OG reading, or at the very least proto-Lucianic. In fact, if indeed OG, this may even reflect an older Hebrew text ויעשו אפד ותרפים, as it alludes to an *ephod*, a vestment of the Yahwistic high priest, in Samaria. The idea of a legitimate Yahwistic (high) priesthood in Samaria would have been highly problematic for the later revisers of (proto-)MT, which may have prompted the omission of this mention here.⁷² La¹¹⁵ thus helps us to find the oldest attainable text in this verse.

The *Gegenprobe*: Lucianic readings confirmed by La¹¹⁵ as recensional in 2 Kings

In addition to the discussion on the putative OG readings of La¹¹⁵, a list of 25 clearest recensional Lucianic readings lacking from La¹¹⁵ will be provided below, indicating that La¹¹⁵ is indeed not a recensional Lucianic witness proper. Most of the cases are those to be found with the pattern La¹¹⁵ = B ≠ L, thus showing that the B-text/majority text is still quite valuable a witness when discerning the OG textual layer of 2 Kgs. While the readings enumerated show quite clear and well-known signs of Lucianic recension (explications of the subjects and actions, better Greek style, small additions and lexical changes, etc.), one should bear in mind that in the *kaige* section there is always a slight change that even the clearest “Lucianic” readings could in fact originate from the OG layer of the text. In these cases, however, at least the witness of La¹¹⁵ would seem to speak against such judgment.

6:6	ξύλον] πρ Ελισσαιε L ⁻⁸² 460
6:7	ὑψωσον σαυτῶ] μετεώρισον καὶ λάβε σεαυτῶ L ⁻⁸² 246 460; <i>leua tibi</i> La ¹¹⁵
6:9	φύλαξαι μὴ παρελθεῖν] πρόσεχε τοῦ μὴ διελθεῖν L ⁻⁸² 460; <i>observa ne transeas</i> La ¹¹⁵ ; <i>cave ne transeas</i> Vulg
6:9	ἐν τῷ τόπῳ τούτῳ] τὸν τόπον τοῦτον L ⁻⁸² 460; om 107'; <i>in locum hunc</i> La ¹¹⁵ ; <i>in loco illo</i> Vulg
6:9	ἐκεῖ Συρία κέκρυπται B 247 a 44 56 64' 488 318 372] ἐκεῖ Σύροι ἐνεδρεύουσιν L ⁻⁸² ; ἐκεῖ post Συρία tr rel; <i>ibi Syria absconsa est</i> La ¹¹⁵
6:13	εἶπεν] + ὁ βασιλεὺς (+Συρίας 246) L ⁻⁸² 246 460
6:14	ἐκεῖ] + (ὁ 19 460) βασιλεὺς Συρίας L ⁻⁸² 246 460
10:12	καὶ ἐπορεύθη] πρ καὶ ἦλθεν A Arm Syr (sub * α'); + Ιου L-700; <i>et abit</i> La ¹¹⁵

⁶⁹ See Tekoniemi, “On the Verge,” (forthcoming); Treballe, “2 Kings 17,7–23,” 223.

⁷⁰ Torijano, “Textual Criticism,” 195–211. See also Tekoniemi, “Between two Differing Editions,” (forthcoming), for an analysis of La¹¹⁵'s agreements with *L* in verses 17:2 and 4.

⁷¹ Cogan & Tadmor, 2 *Kings*, 205–6 (Lucianic); Stade, *Kings*, 264 (marginal gloss).

⁷² See Tekoniemi, “Between Two Differing Editions,” (forthcoming), for further discussion. See Pakkala, *God's Word Omitted*, 183–247, for the phenomenon of similar theological omissions in the Hebrew Bible.

10:12	αὐτὸς ἐν] καὶ αὐτὸς ἦν <i>L</i> -700 460; > αὐτὸς 46' 44-125; <i>ipse</i> <i>La</i> ¹¹⁵
10:29	οὐκ ἀπέστη] + ἀπ' αὐτῶν <i>L</i> -700; <i>non discessit</i> <i>La</i> ¹¹⁵
13:14	πρὸς αὐτὸν] et Ἰωας βασιλεὺς Ἰσραηλ tr <i>L</i> -700 460
13:15	βέλη 1°] βολίδας <i>L</i> -700 460; <i>sagittas</i> <i>La</i> ¹¹⁵
13:15	ἔλαβεν] + Ἰωας <i>L</i> 460
13:16	εἶπεν] + Ἐλισσαιε <i>L</i> 460; + Ἰωας 700; + <i>at ieu</i> <i>La</i> ¹¹⁵
13:19	τρὶς] τρίτον <i>L</i> -700 460; post Συρίαν tr <i>La</i> ¹¹⁵
13:20	ἀπέθανεν] et Ἐλισσαιε tr <i>L</i> -700 460
10:31	Ιου] post ἐφύλαξεν tr <i>L</i> -700 460; om 342
15:32	Ἰουδα] + ἐπὶ (ἐν 93) Ἱερουσαλήμ <i>L</i> -700 328 460
15:33	ἦν] + Ἰωαθαμ <i>L</i> -700
17:5	ἐν πάσῃ τῇ γῆ] ἐπὶ πᾶσαν τὴν γῆν (+ αὐτῆς 19') <i>L</i> -700 460; > πάσῃ V <i>CII</i> ⁻³²⁸ <i>d</i> ⁻³⁷⁰ <i>s</i> ^{-64' 488} 707; om <i>La</i> ¹¹⁵
17:5	Σαμάρειαν] + καὶ εἰς πᾶσαν τὴν γῆν αὐτῆς <i>L</i> ^{-19'} -700 460
17:6	βασιλεὺς Ἀσσυρίων] et τὴν Σαμάρειαν tr <i>L</i> -700 460
17:7	καὶ ἐγένετο] + ὀργὴ κυρίου ἐπὶ τὸν Ἰσραήλ <i>L</i> -700 158; om <i>La</i> ¹¹⁵
17:15	ὀπίσω τῶν ἐθνῶν] καὶ οπισω των θεων των εθνων <i>L</i> ⁻⁹³ -700 460; + των θεων 158; <i>post gentes</i> <i>La</i> ¹¹⁵
17:19	καὶ γε Ἰουδας] καὶ γε καὶ (>82) Ἰουδας καὶ (>700) αὐτός <i>L</i> -700 460; <i>et iudas</i> <i>La</i> ¹¹⁵

Conclusions

In this paper 15 textual cases in 10 verses were studied. Of these 8 were OG agreements with *L* or other Greek witnesses (6:13, 10:8, 11, 29, 13:17, 20₁, 17:6₂, 17), while in 2 cases *La*¹¹⁵ seems to have alone preserved the OG reading against all other witnesses (13:20, 17:6); 2 cases are best attributed to proto-Lucianic layer without deciding their provenance (6:8.1.3); 1 case seems like Lucianic recensional influence on *La*¹¹⁵ (6:8₂); 1 reading is a purely unique reading of *La*¹¹⁵ (10:10₂); and 1 case was too uncertain to assess (10:10₁).

Most of the time the text of *La*¹¹⁵ seems to therefore be a proto-Lucianic (~OG) witness, and sometimes it alone appears to preserve OG readings. There may be some very sporadic contamination from other sources like Lucianic text and possibly even *kaige*. Vulgate could be argued to have influenced *La*¹¹⁵'s text at least once (especially in 17:6), but the similarities are not anywhere striking enough to see this as very probable.

As a conclusion it may thus be said that *La*¹¹⁵ preserves in the studied portions of 2 Kings, like in 1 Kings, a very old and most of the time highly reliable text.

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